

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

D3.3 Data Archive Containing the Downscaled Climate Projections in the Case Studies

VERSION 1

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

This deliverable, namely D3.3, is part of Task 3.3 “Downscaling of future climate projections at the case-study scale and their transfer to the Partners” (Lead: UNIPR/ participants: UPV, UFZ, TUC, IST-ID, CERTE and BU), (Month 1 – Month 26). The aim of D3.3 is to present the future climate data downscaled and corrected at the case-study scale. For the future projections of the precipitation and temperature, the data provided by EURO-CORDEX initiative under two emission scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) are used. For the pilot site located in Greece (Tympaki) also sea level data are provided, since it is affected by saltwater intrusion problem. In this report, the main information on the pilot sites, available data, methods of analysis and data repository are presented.

All the results were treated according to the InTheMED Data Management Plan (Task 1.4) and they are freely downloadable at the link <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7247977> . The data archive also contains specific reports for each pilot site with the aim to support the user in reading and using the data.

1. Introduction

InTheMED focuses on the development of smart models that allow to analyse alternative scenarios and making decisions under different future climate conditions. At this aim, it is necessary to identify potential changes in the main model drivers (precipitation and temperature) that can influence the aquifers under investigation. To better characterize climate variability, it is important to perform local analyses (D’Oria et al., 2018a, 2018b; Todaro et al., 2022). The objective of this work is to present the future climate data for the five pilot sites in the MED, which will be used as input to the smart and calibrated models (see e.g. Secchi et al., 2021). The future precipitation and temperature are given by an ensemble of regional climate models under two Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs): the RCP4.5 and the RCP8.5. For the Greek pilot site, which is affected by saltwater intrusion problem, also future sea level data are provided.

This deliverable describes the data archive of the climate projections provided for each pilot site and freely downloadable at the link <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7247977>. An analysis of the data presented in this report was provided in the Milestone M3.3 “Development of a web repository with the results of the climate change evaluation” (for more details, see Todaro et al., 2022).

2. Pilot Sites and Available Data

The study areas are located in Portugal (Guadiana Basin), Spain (Requena-Utiel), Tunisia (Grombalia), Greece (Tympaki) and Turkey (Konya). The main characteristics of the pilot sites, depicted in Figure 1, are summarized in Table 1. In the following, the pilot sites will be identified with the abbreviations reported in Table 1.

Figure 1. Location of the five pilot sites.

For each pilot site, daily precipitation and mean temperature data were collected over the study areas in the period 1976-2005. The data differ in number and type of gauging stations, amount and source of information. The temperature data refer to the mean values. Table 1 summarizes the main information on the available data; they were mainly provided by the competent national services. Among the available stations, only those that present time series with an amount of data higher than 70% were selected. For the PS-SPA and PS-TUN areas, temperature data at gauging stations were only sporadically available in the period of interest. Then, among of the international web archives, the data from the WATCH Forcing Data dataset (WFD; Weedon et al., 2011) were taken into account.

Regarding the future precipitation and temperature data, the climate projections of the EURO-CORDEX initiative (Jacob et al., 2014) were considered. To account for the uncertainty of the climate model projections, an ensemble of 17 GCM-RCM combinations (Table 2) with a grid resolution of about 12.5 km (EUR-11 grid) under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios were analysed. The RCM simulations start and end on different dates. In this work, a common period for all RCMs was selected, which spans from January the 1st, 1976 to December the 31st, 2098. The RCMs include a historical simulation until 2005 and a scenario period from 2006 to 2098.

Table 1. Main characteristics of the five pilot sites

Nation	Pilot site name	Abbreviation	Size (km ²)	Rain gauge	Temperature gauge	Source of data
Greece	Tympaki	PS-GRE	58	2	1	National Service
Spain	Requena-Utiel	PS-SPA	1285	8	1	National Service (P, T); WFD (T)
Portugal	Guadiana Basin	PS-POR	11594	60	4	National Service
Tunisia	Grombalia	PS-TUN	391	6	1	National Service (P, T); WFD (T)
Turkey	Konya	PS-TUR	50000	18	18	National Service

Table 2. GCM-RCM models from EURO-CORDEX project (<https://www.euro-cordex.net/>). The ditto mark “ indicates repetition of the above text.

	GCM		RCM	
	Institute	Model	Institute	Model
1	CNRM-CERFACS	CNRM-CM5	CLMcom	CCLM4-8-17
2	“	“	SMHI	RCA4
3	“	“	KNMI	RACMO22E
4	ICHEC	EC-EARTH	KNMI	RACMO22E
5	“	“	SMHI	RCA4
6	“	“	CLMcom	CCLM4-8-17
7	“	“	DMI	HIRHAM5
8	IPSL	IPSL-CM5A-MR	IPSL	WRF381P
9	“	“	SMHI	RCA4
10	“	“	IPSL-INNERIS	WRF331F
11	MOHC	HadGEM2-ES	DMI	HIRHAM5
12	“	“	CLMcom	CCLM4-8-17
13	“	“	KNMI	RACMO22E
14	“	“	SMHI	RCA4
15	MPI-M	MPI-ESM-LR	CLMcom	CCLM4-8-17
16	“	“	SMHI	RCA4
17	NCC	NorESM1-M	DMI	HIRHAM5

Regarding the future sea level data, the database provided by the Copernicus Climate Change Service (Yan et al., 2020) was used. The sea level time series are computed using the Deltares Global Tide and Surge Model (GTSM) and the output of the EURO-CORDEX regional climate model HIRHAM5, downscaled from the global climate model EC-EARTH (Model 7 in Table 2). GTSM model is run for two different climate scenarios: the RCP4.5 (for period 2070-2100) and RCP 8.5 (for period 2040-2070). Yan et al. (2022) proposed to start the future climate simulations in 2040, since the large climate variability in sea level takes multiple decades before the climate signal can be detected from the natural climate variability. The authors applied the RCP8.5 pathway for the mid-term future, considering that the present global carbon emissions are tracking above this scenario, and the RCP4.5 for the long-term future (2070-2100), considering that countries will reduce global carbon emissions. It is noteworthy that the projections of these sea level data are based on a single climate model; therefore, the uncertainty associated with this data is not determinable.

3. Methods

3.1. Historical Data

Following the guidelines defined by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO, 2016) to perform the bias correction, at least 30 years of continuous time series of observed data are required; a common period to perform the bias corrections is 1976-2005. For this reason, it is necessary to fill the gaps in the historical time series. For each station, the gaps in the records were filled according to a linear relationship with the best correlated neighbouring gauge (Allen et al., 1998), according to the Pearson correlation coefficient. In the absence of contemporary daily information, the missing data were replaced with random values extracted from a normal (for temperature) and log-normal (for precipitation) distributions, with mean and standard deviation computed from the recorded data. To preserve seasonality, this method was applied on monthly scale (i.e. each month of the available sample has its own mean and standard deviation). In case of precipitation, the probability of no-rain was preserved.

To fill the temperature time series using the WATCH Forcing dataset, the four closest cells to the meteorological station are considered. Then, the temperatures are replaced with the one available at the grid node that presents the best correlation with the few observed data.

3.2. Regional Climate Model Data

The future daily precipitation and daily mean temperature were acquired from an ensemble of 17 RCM models (Table 2), which are part of the EURO-CORDEX initiative. Climate models are characterized by systematic model errors (bias) that should be corrected before using the projections for local impact and vulnerability assessment studies (Teutschbein and Seibert, 2010).

The models provide results on a regular grid with a resolution of 0.11° (EUR-11, ~ 12.5 km). The climate model data were downscaled at the climate station locations and bias corrected with reference to the historical control period 1976-2005. In particular, for the downscaling procedure, the Inverse Weighted Distance method was used by interpolating the climate data at the nine nodes closest to the considered meteorological station (D'Oria et al., 2017).

The bias correction was performed following the distribution mapping method (D’Oria et al., 2017, 2018; Teutschbein and Seibert, 2012) which ensures that cumulative distribution functions of the climate model data, at monthly scale, agree with the ones of the observed data in the control period. The same correction estimated for the historical period is then applied for the future, since the assumption usually made is that the correction identified for the control period holds for the scenario runs (Teutschbein and Seibert, 2013). The Gamma distribution and the Gaussian distribution are used to model the wet-day rainfall and the temperature time series, respectively. Prior to the Distribution Mapping correction, the wet-day frequencies were adjusted identifying an RCM-specific threshold such that the number of rainy days in the model is equal to the one of the observed data. Then, all days with precipitation below the threshold were considered dry.

4. Data Archive

The data archive *InTheMED_WP3_DS_ClimateData.zip* contains observed and simulated daily precipitation and daily mean temperature. The observed data spans from January the 1st, 1976 to December the 31st, 2005. The future climate data are provided for 17 RCMs and two Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) in the period from January the 1st, 1976 to December the 31st, 2098.

There are five folders, one for each pilot site, named: Greece, Portugal, Spain, Tunisia and Turkey. Each folder includes a report summarizing the data for the specific pilot site and two MATLAB data structures containing the precipitation and temperature data. The files are named:

- Data_report_###.docx
- P_RCM_corr_###.mat
- T_RCM_corr_###.mat

where ### has to be replaced with the folder name.

The folder Greece also includes the MATLAB data structure SeaLevel_Greece containing the sea level data.

P_RCM_corr_###.mat

The MAT-file P_RCM_corr_###.mat contains the observed and RCM precipitation (bias corrected and raw data) for all the precipitation stations (#Pstat). In particular, the MAT-file includes the following variables:

- station_code [#Pstat x 1]: vector containing the #Pstat station codes;
- station_name [#Pstat x 1]: vector containing the #Pstat station names;
- mod_name [17 x 1]: vector containing the 17 RCM names;

- `time_obs` [10958 x 1]: datetime vector containing the daily dates of the observed data in the control period (from 1-Jan-1976 to 31-Dec-2005);
- `time_RCM_corr` [44926 x 1]: datetime vector containing the daily of the RCM data (from 1-Jan-1976 to 31-Dec-2098);
- `p_obs` [10958 x #Pstat]: observed daily precipitation in the control period (from 1-Jan-1976 to 31-Dec-2005) at the #Pstat stations, downstream the filling process. The data order is the same of `station_name`;
- `p_RCM_all_Corr` [44926 x #Pstat x 17 x 2]: 4D matrix containing the daily precipitation bias corrected of the 17 models for the #Pstat station locations and the two RCP scenarios. The data order is the same of `station_name` and `mod_name`. For example, the value `p_RCM_all_corr(i,j,k,l)` is the precipitation on day `time_RCM_corr(i)`, at location of `station_name(j)`, given by the `mod_name(k)` for the RCP scenario `l`;
- `p_RCM_all_NoCorr` [44926 x #Pstat x 17 x 2]: 4D matrix, similar to `p_RCM_all_corr` matrix, containing the raw daily precipitation before the bias correction.

T_RCM_corr_###.mat

The MAT-file `T_RCM_corr_###.mat` contains the observed and RCM mean temperature data for the #Tstat stations. The MAT-file contains the following variables:

- `station_code` [#Tstat x 1]: vector containing the #Tstat station codes;
- `station_name` [#Tstat x 1]: vector containing the #Tstat station names;
- `mod_name` [17 x 1]: vector containing the 17 RCM names;
- `time_obs` [10958 x 1]: datetime vector containing the daily dates of the observed data in the control period (from 1-Jan-1976 to 31-Dec-2005);
- `time_RCM_corr` [44926 x 1]: datetime vector containing the daily dates of the RCM data (from 1-Jan-1976 to 31-Dec-2098);

- `t_obs` [10958 x #Tstat]: observed daily mean temperature in the control period (from 1-Jan-1976 to 31-Dec-2005) at the #Tstat stations, downstream the filling process. The data order is the same of `station_name`;
- `t_RCM_all_Corr` [44926 x #Tstat x 17 x 2]: 4D matrix containing the daily mean temperature bias corrected of the 17 models for the #Tstat station locations and the two RCP scenarios. The data order is the same of `station_name` and `mod_name`. For example, the value `t_RCM_all_corr(i,j,k,l)` is the temperature on day `time_RCM_corr(i)`, at location of `station_name(j)`, given by the `mod_name(k)` for the RCP scenario `l`;
- `t_RCM_all_NoCorr` [44926 x #Tstat x 17 x 2]: 4D matrix, similar to `t_RCM_all_corr` matrix, containing the raw daily mean temperature before the bias correction.

SeaLevel_Greece.mat

The MAT-file `SeaLevel_Greece.mat` contains the future mean sea level height relative to the historical mean sea level for the coastal grid point closest to Tympaki. In particular, the MAT-file includes the following variables:

- `node_coord` [2 x 1]: vector containing the longitude and latitude of the coastal grid point;
- `mod_name` [1 x 1]: vector containing the RCM name;
- `SeaLevel_MT_85` [30 x 1]: vector containing the annual relative mean sea level at the location defined in `node_coord` for the mid-term period (2041-2070) under the RCP 8.5 scenario;
- `SeaLevel_LT_45` [30 x 1]: vector containing the annual relative mean sea level at the location defined in `node_coord` for the long-term period (2071-2100) under the RCP4.5 scenario;
- `time_85` [30 x 1]: vector containing the year of projected data `SeaLevel_MT_85`;
- `time_45` [30 x 1]: vector containing the year of projected data `SeaLevel_LT_45`.

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